
THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE RULE OF THE SHAIBANI DYNASTY IN MOVAROUNNAHR

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7792842>

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Abstract

This article provides information about the consequences of the crisis of the Timurid state in the 16th century, the political situation in Movarounnahr on the eve of the establishment of the Shaybanid state. At the same time, this article reveals the emergence of a new state in our region - the state of Shaybanites, their efforts to unify the country. and relations with the Safavid state were also touched upon.

Keywords

Movarounnahr, Uzbek Ulusi, Abulhairkhan, Shaybanikhan, Khoja Abulmakorim, Babur, Ismail Shah, Mirza Husayn Boykara.

Introduction

The ruler of the "Uzbek Ulusi", Abulhairkhan, knew very well the situation of the time in which he lived. He took into account the conditions of Central Asia at that time and knew that there was no chance, so he did not give in to the idea of conquest, on the contrary, he was satisfied with occasionally helping the descendants of Timur, who were drowning in each other's blood and quarreling. He did not look only for the benefit of Abu Said. Manuchehr supported Mirza and Sultan Husayn Boykara. Abulhairkhan's Uzbeks always returned with a lot of booty. His reign of nearly forty years is considered the most glorious period of the desert khanate.

Turkmens have a proverb: "The people of the desert disperse very quickly, but the happiness of people spreads even faster". Abulhairkhan's arrogance prepared his enemies and envious people to assassinate him. The desert khans in his army united against him. Even his relatives like the above Burga Sultan joined them. According to the Tatar proverb, "If the enemy attacks your father's land, you will join them and fight together" and they all attacked him together. So he became weak. After his death, many influential family members dispersed to all parts of the

desert. Of the eleven sons left after him, only the fifth son, Sheikh Haydar Sultan, remained in his place, but he also had nothing but a dry name. That is why his influence and power was short-lived. The Uzbeks focused their attention and trust on Abulkhair's grandson Muhammad Shaybani (1451-1510), who was called Shahbakht. Despite his youth, this breed gave birth to the brightest hopes for the future.

The Main part

Shaybanikhan (1451-1510) orphaned by his father Budok Sultan and his mother Kozibegim at a young age, he lived with his brother under the protection of his father's loyal servant Karachabek. Karachabek served this Prince with perfect loyalty. After the death of Sheikh Haidar, Karachabek was forced to flee from the enemies of the Abulkhayr family to the lower reaches of the Syrdarya River, taking these orphaned princes. When Shaybanikhan returned from here, he gathered around him the people of his great-grandfather's army, who were scattered in different directions, under the pretext of taking holy blood revenge. After the necessary preparations, he decided to restore the lost glory of the dynasty. In particular, Burga, who betrayed Abulhairkhan and lived at the foot of a forest on the upstream side of the Syrdarya, took revenge on the Sultan. Shaibanikhan hypocritically made friends with Burga Sultan until he gathered strength and prepared. When the preparations were over, the most vengeful of men, a true terror of the wilderness, attacked the palace of his enemy, Burga, with his three loyal companions on one of the long winter nights. He executed many of his family members and relatives. The escaped Burga Sultan did not escape death either, Shaybani found him and executed him. After this successful attack, the young prince became the leader of the newly strengthened Uzbek cavalry. Under their protection, he found an opportunity to participate in battles. When the situation in the center went like this, it was impossible not to clash with the Timurids. During this period, the owner of the throne of Samarkand was Abusaid's son Sultan Ahmad (1694-1494).

The deputy of the northern border of the country was Majid Tarkhan, son of Khushliq Khan. Shaybani asked him to take him into his service, Majid Tarkhan agreed, and also set a salary. But Majid sent them to the governor of Bukhara, Abdulali Tarkhan, to escape from danger. The palace of the absolute ruler of Bukhara, Abdulali Tarkhan, was not inferior to the palace of his subordinate ruler in terms of decoration and luxury. He welcomed the Uzbeks and took advantage of them when the Mongols attacked from the northeast. When the privileged governors of the northern provinces of Turkestan rebelled, Abulkhair's successors

were used to suppress the rebellion. But the Uzbek princes began to be dissatisfied with the simple salary paid for any armed service, either because they felt that this land was their motherland or because of the influence of their accumulated forces. Therefore, it was considered necessary to give them the cities of Utror, Sovron, and Signoq.

The princes were supported by many of their supporters and the children of the desert who loved heroic actions from the back, so it was natural that the peaceful relationship between the Shaibanis who were coming to the field and the Timurids, who were in crisis, would not last long. The cause of the collision was quickly found. During the lifetime of Sultan Ahmed, Shaibani thought about the future and seized Sirdarya belonging to Naib Majid Tarkhan as a victim. The extremely strong military spirit of the young nomadic khans was enough for their conflicts and battles, besides, the extremely complicated political life of Movarounnahr and the leadership of the beys caused Shaybani to conquer the country. He invaded Samarkand for the first time in 905/1500. According to the information of the author of "Shaybaniname", Shaybani's brother Sultan Mahmud Boysunqur attacked the surroundings of Jizzakh during Mirza's time and had to retreat with great losses. Shaibani reprimanded his brother for launching an attack without warning and immediately crossed the Syrdarya river with a thousand men to avenge the defeat. But his campaign was unsuccessful due to the treachery of the soldiers. Shaybani was forced to go back.

Sheikh Mansour was Shaybani's teacher. He came to the idea of conquering countries in accordance with the symbolic words of his elder: "It is necessary to start from the edges, not the middle". First of all, he sent an appeal to the surrounding Turkish beys, urging them to completely end the rule of the Timurids. It meant that the time had come. Despite the fact that the foundations of the Timurids' power were rotten and loose, there were still many Turks loyal to the ruler of Samarkand. In any case, Shaybani considered it necessary to attract all of them to his side and succeeded in this. The most important among them were Kochim Sultan, Suyunchhoja Sultan, Hamza Sultan and Mahdi Sultan. After that, he is his former self fulfilled his intention and marched on Samarkand with a well-prepared army. After Babur returned from here to Andijan, Sultan Ali, who remained at the head of the state, was the governor in name only. Great-grandfather Khoja Abulmakorim (real name Khoja Yahya), who has been serving as Shaykhulislam in Samarkand for 400 years, was a real governor. But both of them were uneducated for leadership and were not capable of repelling the danger threatening the country. After a ten-day siege, when the attack from the

Shaikhzada gate was successfully repulsed, Shaybani entered through the Crossroads gate, reached Bogi Nav and defeated the enemy army. The war began in the middle of the day. Shaybani faced death and personally participated in the war. The killing continued on both sides throughout the night. The next day, Baqi Tarkhan, the son of Abdulali Tarkhan, who served Shaybani, came to help Samarkand, and it was reported that he had built a camp near the Dabusiya fortress. In this regard, the Uzbeks released Samarkand from the siege and quickly retreated to Bukhara. Bukhara, which lost all its auxiliary soldiers, had no choice but to surrender unconditionally to the Uzbeks. Shaibanikhan made Bukhara his headquarters. After settling his mother and family in the palace here, he marched on Karakol with his army. Because after this land was conquered for the first time, the protection parts left under the chairmanship of Boboy Sultan were violently overthrown. Therefore, it was necessary to conquer it anew. However, it was possible to re-besiege Samarkand only after punishing the rebels with all the severity of Uzbek military law.

Samarkand was besieged again, and the people of the city put up a fierce resistance for nine months. If the conflict between the righteous Khoja Abulmakorim and Khan Sultan Ali did not turn into open enmity, perhaps the date of occupying this strong fortress could be pushed back a little. Shaibanikhan, who was well aware of this conflicting situation, said to the ruler of Samarkand, Sultan Ali: "Have you not yet had enough of living under the guardianship of the Khoja, is it not yet time to congratulate the star who was born with grace from the house of Abulkhair and seek your life on the path of friendship with him?" wrote a letter in the content. Shaybanikhan asked Sultan Ali's mother to marry him to show that his offer of friendship was written with good intentions. Sultan Ali's mother agreed. These affairs were kept secret to such an extent that one Friday Shaibani Muhammadkhan entered the besieged city of Samarkand from one side. Completely unaware of this, Khoja Abulmakorim was sitting in the mosque on the other side of the city. This event happened in 906 (1500). The people of Samarkand, who were in a hurry, accepted their fate. A marriage was arranged between Uzbek Khan and Zuhra Beg, Sultan Ahmed's widowed wife. Sultan Ali died soon after that.

Shaybanikhan treated the supporters of the previous dynasty extremely harshly and mercilessly, causing people danger and terror. Thanks to this, after making a deal with his brother, who was creating danger and anxiety against him around Uratepa, he was able to cross the Amudarya with a small army and start moving. The contentment and humility of the Uzbek conqueror, the level of

patience and heroism was very surprising. As soon as he took the throne of Samarkand, Shaibani began to be attracted by the pastures of Khorasan. But there, on the throne of Herat, sat the strong and passionate Mirza Husayn Boykara. He was aware of Shaibani's condition. Therefore, he hesitated to start direct hostilities against Boykara, and began to attack the weak areas of Khurasan, subject to the authority of Mirza Husayn. The first of these was Balkh, where Prince Badiuzzamon raised the flag of rebellion against Mirza Husain. The second one was the lands belonging to the former minister of Sultan Ahmed, Khisravshah, after Shaibanikhan excluded his patron's sons by denying them, he added Hisar, Khatlon, Kunduz, Badakhshan to his country. Before going to war with Mirza Husain, Shaybani Khan felt it necessary to protect the rear of his country from danger, that is, to fight and defeat Babur's Mongolian relatives Khanika Sultan and Olacha Sultan. On the right bank of the Syrdarya, in the vicinity of Shahrukhiya and Tashkent, there were many armies of them, consisting of Mongols and Kalmyks. Partly out of envy, partly to take revenge on their unfortunate brother Babur (1483-1530), they harmed the Uzbeks in various ways.

Finally, on a cold winter day, Shaibanikhan marched north with an army wrapped in furs. Together with his brothers Sultan Mahmud and Timur Sultan, they formed a vanguard of 6,000 brave Uzbeks. they did not achieve anything, and in the gray deserts, the ferocious fervor in Shaybani's heart died down, he returned to Samarkand, and the Mongols pursued him to Oratepa. Although this city was recaptured the following summer and a treaty was concluded with Khanika Sultan, in reality it was not a truce but an event. As soon as Shaybanikhan invaded Khysravshah's property, the Mongols again started hostile action against Shaybani Khan. This time they attacked not only the border areas, but also the land of Tanbal Sultan, Shaybani's deputy in Khoqand. Tanbal had the right to expect help from Shaybani, because, firstly, he was the one who caused the loss of Babur's throne with his conspiracy, and secondly, he did not have the strength to resist the Uzbek attack. There were no other reasons for Shaibanikhan to give up his current foreign aggressions and put all his strength against his enemies in Turan. Shaybanikhan was brave and ambitious by nature, and if the Mongols living between the Syrdarya and the Gobi desert and the Timurids, who were dependent on the Khanikas, formed an alliance, it was clear that they would destroy all the plans and goals of the Uzbeks. Since Shaybanikhan understood this very well, in 911/1505 he first marched on Shahrukhiya with all his military power and ordered to besiege it. Then he marched along the Syrdarya River and reached Akhsi, fifteen miles from where the Mongol army was united and ready for battle. The author of

“Shaybaniname” describes some characteristics of the armies of both sides and depicts the biggest of these bloody battles, which ended with the victory of the Uzbeks, in a very lively and interesting way.

Khanika and his brother were captured and brought to Shaibanikhan. While they, no doubt, expected death, Shaybanikhan granted them safety and showed great nobility, even telling some stories and comforting them because they had met with a disaster. He calmed them down by telling them not to touch themselves, their relatives, or their property. Shaibanikhan demanded the surrender of Shahrukhiya fortress, which was commanded by their mothers. Hearing that her children were treated with kindness and nobility, this woman's heart softened, she surrendered the castle of her own free will, and obtained peace in return. After getting rid of the opponents in the rear, Shaibanikhan now turned his attack on his opponents on the left bank of the Amudarya. But the situation here has changed a little. Hisar, Kunduz, Khatlon, Badakhshan governor Khisravshah and the begs under Sultan Husayn Mirza, despite all their efforts to gain freedom, the conflicts between them continued fiercely, but they noticed the appearance of a common danger and stood against Shaibani Khan. they formed an alliance and joined together. But although these allies used all their measures in practice, they did not achieve any success.

Shaibani Khan had first started a war against Khisravshah. However, Shaibanikhan refrained from a new war because of Tanbalkhan's rebellion against his father. Therefore, Shaibani was forced to send a new force to the northwestern border of his country. The blasphemy of the rebellion ended with the loss of life for Nemat Tanbalkhan along with his seven brothers and sisters. Following Genghis and Timur, Shaibanikhan took the post of supreme commander. Formerly a wanderer in the deserts, this man rose to the rank of ruler of several lands by force of arms and reunified Movarounnahr. After the battle between Ismail Shah and Shaibanikhan, the power of the Iranian Shah Ismail Safavi was established in Khorezm, but the people of Khorezm organized a conspiracy against him. In 1511, Khorezm separated from the Shaybani state and raised Elbars, the son of Berka sultan, as its khan. In this way, the independent Khanate of Khiva was created.

Conclusion

As a general conclusion, it can be said that the last successors of Amir Timur, who finished the brightest pages in the history of Uzbek statehood, the Shaybanites who took power from them in the 16th century, and the dynasties that ruled the power in the future could not maintain these successes and the level of development in statehood. At the same time, through this article, we can see that in

the 16th century, the relations between Iran and the two countries that appeared in Central Asia at the same time became very tense.

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